

A dual-duplex RT-dPCR surveillance strategy for discriminating avian and seasonal influenza viruses in wastewater

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Abstract

The highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) A(H5Nx) viruses, specifically those of clade 2.3.4.4b, remain a major concern for global animal and public health. The current epidemiological situation in Europe and beyond reveal an alarming increase in spread and occurrence of these viruses, underscoring the need for enhanced surveillance and proactive intervention measures.

We propose a dual duplex strategy (combining CDC Flu SC2 multiplex and JRC HA-JRC MP duplex assays) for discriminating avian and seasonal influenza viruses in wastewater, supporting rapid strain-specific environmental monitoring.

Current Epidemiological Context and Study Rationale

Between 2024 and 2026, the global incidence of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) A(H5Nx) of clade 2.3.4.4b has experienced a dramatic increase, resulting in the infection of millions of wild and domestic birds, posing a significant threat to biodiversity, and causing substantial economic losses in the food production sector [1, 2]. The extensive circulation, ongoing evolution of the virus and ecological circumstances have increased the probability of mammalian spillover [3]. Since March 2024, the United States (US) has reported over 1,084 cases of infection of HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b in dairy cattle across 19 states, with additional infections in other mammals, including domestic cats. Overall, 71 human cases, mostly linked to exposure to infected cattle and poultry were reported, with 2 fatalities [4-6].

The 2025 autumn wave (September-November) in Europe saw a record-high 2,896 detections of HPAI A(H5) virus of clade 2.3.4.4b in 29 countries, surpassing all previous seasonal counts since systematic monitoring began. The majority of these cases (2,454 i.e., 85%) were found in wild birds, including mass-mortality events in species such as the common crane, while 442 outbreaks were reported in domestic birds, primarily turkeys [7].

The viral environmental contamination caused by infected wild birds has repeatedly led to outbreaks in poultry farms, highlighting the constant risk of spillover to domestic birds and lateral spread among farms. In addition, cross-species transmission in livestock remains a pressing concern also outside the US, as evidenced by the first detection of H5N1 antibodies in a Dutch

dairy cow, that followed the detection of HPAI A(H5) 2.3.4.4b virus in a cat from the same farm [8, 9].

According to current risk assessments by the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC), the risk of infection posed by A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b viruses for the general EU population is considered low, but it is classified as low-to-moderate for occupationally exposed groups [7]. At the same time, the increased frequency of mammalian infections driven by the widespread circulation of HPAI A(H5) virus of clade 2.3.4.4b in wild birds and poultry and consequent environmental contamination, may create additional opportunities for occurrence of adaptive mutations, reassortment, and the progressive accumulation of traits associated with enhanced zoonotic/pandemic potential [10]. In this constantly evolving scenario, continuous, specific, and integrated surveillance strategies are key for the timely monitoring of HPAI A(H5) clade 2.3.4.4b viruses across species and in the environment.

Wastewater and environmental surveillance (WES) stands as a crucial tool for monitoring infectious diseases at the population-level in a cost-effective manner [10-12], allowing for timely detection of emerging threats and assessment of intervention impacts [13]. In Europe this approach is already being operationalised through the European Commission's wastewater-surveillance framework-comprising the Wastewater Observatory for Public Health, the GLOWACON network, the EU-WISH joint action and the EU Wastewater Sentinel System -backed by > €60 M of DG HERA funding and aligned with WHO guidance, thereby paving the way for the establishment of an early-warning system for avian influenza [14].

WES typically relies on polymerase chain reaction (PCR) based methods to determine and/or quantify the presence of specific pathogens within a community in a specific time frame [15]. WES was widely used for SARS-CoV-2 [14], and was later extended also to respiratory pathogens including influenza A and B. The M gene is the preferred molecular target for the screening of Influenza A viruses [16], due to its conservation across seasonal and animal influenza strains and relative abundance. Consequently, no molecular-based assay employed in WES is capable of distinguishing seasonal influenza viruses from HPAI A(H5) 2.3.4.4b strains in a single test. This feature is exemplified by the CDC Influenza-SARS-CoV-2 Multiplex Assay (CDC-Flu SC2) [17], one of the most widely adopted platforms for routine influenza surveillance, which detects

influenza A (FluA), influenza B (FluB), and SARS-CoV-2 with high sensitivity but does not differentiate between seasonal influenza subtypes and HPAI A(H5) 2.3.4.4b viruses [18]. This inability could potentially hamper the utility of wastewater-based surveillance preventing the promptness of strain-specific monitoring.

Recently, we developed two RT-PCR based assays, the JRC-HA and JRC-MP, which specifically target highly conserved elements within the hemagglutinin and matrix protein genes of the HPAI A(H5Nx) 2.3.4.4b genome, respectively [18]. Assays were optimized to be run both as real-time (RT-qPCR) and digital (RT-dPCR) formats. In comparison to the CDC-Flu SC2 Multiplex Assay, our JRC assays have demonstrated higher sensitivity and specificity in detecting HPAI A(H5Nx) 2.3.4.4b viruses circulating in Italy in 2023. *In silico*, their inclusivity was satisfactory across sequences from strains collected worldwide till June 2025 [18]. In particular, the JRC-HA assay showed high specificity when evaluated on Italian wastewater samples, detecting avian influenza only when spiked, and demonstrating tolerance to matrix inhibitors. Synthetic RNAs representing human influenza A (H1N1) and B were also analyzed, demonstrating the absence of cross-reactivity of the JRC-HA assay against human influenza.

In response to the current epidemiological situation and as a preparedness action to monitor the spread of HPAI viruses, this study aims to: (i) confirm the efficacy of the JRC assays against the contemporary HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b viruses collected between Oct-Dec 2025 in Italy; (ii) assess the performance of the JRC assays in simulated wastewater scenarios that mimic realistic HPAI A co-circulation conditions of (H5N1) clade 2.3.4.4b and seasonal influenza virus; and (iii) propose a comprehensive dual-duplex surveillance strategy consisting of the JRC HA and MP duplex and the CDC-Flu SC2 assay for enhanced environmental detection of HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b viruses.

Validation Against Current Circulating Strains

We verified the performance of the JRC-HA and JRC-MP assays using HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b viruses circulating in northern Italy during October - December 2025 in wild birds and poultry (Figure 1 A). Sequence alignment analysis revealed a high degree of conservation in the regions

recognised by the primers-probe of both the JRC HA and JRC MP assays, indicating that ongoing virus evolution did not substantially alter these regions, and thus confirming the assays high inclusivity (Figure 1 B).

A

SAMPLE ID	Sample	Matrix	GISAID Isolate ID	Genotype	
				Genin	ggFLU
A	A/turkey/Italy/25VIR8933-13/2025	Tracheal Swab	EPI_ISL_20207397	EA-2024-DIDI.2.1	B.18
B	A/mallard/Italy/25VIR10761-1/2025	Cloacal Swab	EPI_ISL_20282404	EA-2024-DIDI.2.1	--
C	A/eurasian-wigeon/Italy/25VIR9558-3/2025	Tracheal Swab	EPI_ISL_20237305	EA-2024-DIDI.2.1	B.18
D	A/yellow-legged-gull/Italy/25VIR10550-1/2025	Organ pool	EPI_ISL_20282392	EA-2024-DIDI.2.1	--
E	A/mute-swan/Italy/25VIR10388-2/2025	Organ	EPI_ISL_20261558	EA-2024-DIDI.2.1	B.18
F	A/mute-swan/Italy/25VIR10598-1/2025	SNC	EPI_ISL_20282395	EA-2024-DIDI.2.1	--
G	A/chicken/Italy/25VIR10798-1/2025	Organ pool	EPI_ISL_20282406	EA-2024-DIDI.2.1	--
H	A/turkey/Italy/25VIR10392-1/2025	Tracheal Swab	EPI_ISL_20286945	EA-2024-DIDI.2.1	--
I	A/muscovy-duck/Italy/25VIR10762-1/2025	Cloacal Swab	EPI_ISL_20261564	EA-2024-DIDI.2.1	B.18
J	A/chicken/Italy/25VIR10912-4/2025	Tracheal Swab	EPI_ISL_20282387	EA-2024-DIDI.2.1	--

B

HA sequence alignment

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JRC-HA method      ACTGGGCTCAGAAATAGTCCTC          AGAGGGAGGATGCCAGGGAAATGGTT          CATCATAGCAATGAGCAAGGGGA
JRC-HA amplicon    ACTGGGCTCAGAAATAGTCCTCTAAGAGAAAAGAGAAAAGAGGCTCTTTTGGGGCGATAGCCAGGGTTTATAGAGGGAGGATGCCAGGGAAATGGTTGATGGTTGGTATGGGTACCATCATAGCAATGAGCAAGGGGA

A  EPI_ISL_20207397 .....G.....C.....T.....A.....
B  EPI_ISL_20282404 .....G.....C.....T.....A.....
C  EPI_ISL_20237305 .....G.....C.....T.....A.....C.....
D  EPI_ISL_20282392 .....G.....C.....T.....A.....C.....
E  EPI_ISL_20261558 .....G.....C.....T.....A.....C.....
F  EPI_ISL_20282395 .....G.....C.....T.....A.....C.....
G  EPI_ISL_20282406 .....G.....C.....T.....A.....C.....
H  EPI_ISL_20286945 .....G.....C.....T.....A.....G.....C.....
I  EPI_ISL_20261564 .....G.....C.....T.....A.....G.....C.....
J  EPI_ISL_20282387 .....G.....C.....T.....A.....G.....C.....
NL Cat  EPI_ISL_20304129 .....G.....C.....T.....A.....C.....

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MP sequence alignment

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JRC-MP method      TGTCTTTGCAGGGGAAGAACACC ATCTTGAAGGCTCTCATGGAATGGCT          GATTTGTGTTCACGCTCACCGT
JRC-MP amplicon    TGTCTTTGCAGGGGAAGAACACCATCTTGAAGGCTCTCATGGAATGGCTAAAGACAAAGACCAATCTGTACCTCTGACTAAGGGGATTTTGGGATTTGTGTTCACGCTCACCGT

A  EPI_ISL_20207397 .....A.....
B  EPI_ISL_20282404 .....A.....
C  EPI_ISL_20237305 .....A.....A.....
D  EPI_ISL_20282392 .....A.....
E  EPI_ISL_20261558 .....A.....
F  EPI_ISL_20282395 .....A.....
G  EPI_ISL_20282406 .....A.....
H  EPI_ISL_20286945 .....A.....
I  EPI_ISL_20261564 .....A.....
J  EPI_ISL_20282387 .....A.....
NL Cat  EPI_ISL_20304129 .....A.....

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Figure 1. Description of the samples. A. Bird samples (A-J) were collected from October to December 2025 during passive and active surveillance activities in wild and domestic birds in North-East Italy. The presence of HPAI (H5N1) 2.3.4.4b virus was confirmed by RT-qPCR and WGS methods in use at the EU and National reference laboratory for

AI/ND. **B.** Sequence alignment of the HA- and MP specific primer/probe sets with the corresponding hybridization genome regions of: i) the amplicon, as the most frequently observed sequence targeted by the assay in the United States outbreak sequence segments deposited in GISAID (December 2024) for which the assays were originally designed ii) A-J HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b viruses iii) the HPAI (H5N1) 2.3.4.4b-positive cat sample identified in the Netherlands in the same farm with seropositive dairy cattle. Mutations in the oligonucleotide binding sites are highlighted in red, while mutations within the amplicons are indicated in bold.

Accordingly, *in silico* PCR simulation predicted positive amplification when using these samples as templates (allowing maximum five mismatches on the annealing regions of oligonucleotides, data not shown). In line with the *in silico* PCR predictions, RT-qPCR results showed that both the JRC assays successfully detected all tested samples, including those with lower virus concentrations (high C_q values, Figure 2A). RT-dPCR confirmed these results for both JRC-assays (Figure 2B).

Figure 2. Verification of the JRC- HA and JRC- MP assays inclusivity against recent HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b viruses from Italy. A and B. RT-qPCR (A) and RT-dPCR (B) results obtained analysing RNA extracted by the HPAI A(H5N1) clade 2.3.4.4b clinical samples from Italy (described in Figure 1) with the CDC Flu SC2 multiplex assay targeting FluA and FluB (data not shown), the JRC-HA assay and the JRC-MP assay samples listed in Figure 1. All assay conditions were identical to those described

previously [18], with the exception of the annealing temperature, which after re-adaptation to the new variants, was adjusted to 56.4 °C (instead of the previously used 60 °C) in the RT-dPCR format.

The FluA primer set of the CDC Flu SC2 multiplex assay [17] also detected HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b in A-J samples, confirming its broad influenza A reactivity at levels that are comparable to that of the JRC assays, as assessed by Cq values and copies/ μL values.

While this breadth is valuable to avoid false negative results during screening, it becomes clear that this feature does not permit discrimination between seasonal and novel influenza viruses (including HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b) when present in the same specimen, e.g., environmental or wastewater samples collected during the European/North-American autumn-winter period. To circumvent this, partnerships between the CDC and private laboratories were established to widen testing capacity to Influenza A(H5) as well. In agreement with this strategy, in our study, we have combined the CDC Flu SC2 multiplex assay with the JRC-HA/JRC-M assays to improve laboratory testing and allow a faster and sensitive detection of HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b in animal and human populations.

Simulated Wastewater Performance Under Co-Circulation Scenarios

In the absence of confirmed European HPAI A(H5) 2.3.4.4b-positive wastewater samples, we prepared artificial samples to simulate three different epidemiological scenarios reflecting varying patterns of seasonal and HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b influenza virus RNA concentrations that might occur in the event of avian influenza spillover to humans. RNA extracts from wastewater samples that tested negative for both avian and human influenza were spiked with a designated amount of HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b and human seasonal influenza A RNAs. This approximated real field conditions (Figure 3).

Scenario I – HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b-Only: When no seasonal-influenza RNA was present, the JRC-HA, JRC-MP and the FluA primer set of the CDC-Flu SC2 duplex assays all yielded positive signals for the low-level HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b spike. Quantitatively, the corresponding copies μL^{-1} were statistically indistinguishable across the three assays. This confirms that, within a wastewater RNA background, the JRC assays operate close to their analytical limits [18] while

the CDC assay - although originally designed for human influenza A- still generates an equivalent quantitative response for the avian virus

Scenario II - Low levels of HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b and seasonal influenza A: This scenario simulated conditions with reduced concentrations of seasonal influenza (approximately 35 RNA copies) and HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b (approximately 10 and 20 copies), which might occur during the emergence or decline of seasonal influenza or in populations with lower seasonal circulation and low prevalence of avian influenza. The results showed that while the JRC-HA and MP assays maintained their specificity for HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b, the FluA primer set of the CDC-Flu SC2 recognised both avian and seasonal influenza viruses without distinction and quantitatively reflected the presence of both strains.

Scenario III – Low level HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b with high seasonal influenza A background: This scenario simulated the emergence of HPAI during peak seasonal influenza activity, with approximately 3,500 RNA copies of seasonal influenza with 10 and 20 copies HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b. The JRC-HA assay specifically detected only avian influenza virus signals, demonstrating absence of cross-reactivity with seasonal influenza. Notably, the JRC-MP detected both avian and seasonal influenza viruses, with approximately 14-fold lower detected copy number compared to the CDC-Flu SC2 assay (250 versus 3,500 copies), providing, provided additional discriminatory value and confirmed the suboptimal performance of the JRC-MP against influenza viruses other than HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b.

The spiked RNAs were analysed by RT-dPCR with the QIAcuity Four 5-plex digital PCR system (Qiagen) using the duplex JRC-HA and JRC-MP assay, and the CDC-Flu SC2 duplex FluA and FluB (not shown) assay as previously described [18]. Overall, these simulations demonstrate that the JRC-HA and JRC-MP assays reliably detect low-level HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b in wastewater even when seasonal influenza is present at concentrations of more than 2 log₁₀ higher. In contrast, the CDC-Flu SC2 duplex assay, although it detects both avian and human influenza viruses, confirms its inability to discriminate HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b from seasonal influenza.

Figure 3. Dual-duplex performance in simulated wastewater co-occurrence scenarios. RNA extracts from wastewater samples that tested negative for both avian and human influenza were spiked with the indicated copy numbers of HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b and human seasonal influenza A. Statistical significance was determined using t-Test *** = $P < 0.0001$; ns: not significant. Error bars indicate the mean value \pm SD.

Dual-Duplex Integration Strategy for Enhanced Surveillance

Our data demonstrate that the JRC-HA and JRC-MP duplex assays provide highly specific and sensitive detection of low-level HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b in wastewater, even in the presence of seasonal influenza concentrations that are more than 2 log₁₀ higher. At the same time, the CDC Flu SC2 multiplex assay continues to deliver reliable, broad-spectrum surveillance of influenza A, influenza B and SARS-CoV-2, preserving the existing monitoring infrastructure.

To promptly identify spillover events of HPAI A(H5N1) 2.3.4.4b in the human population, we therefore propose a dual-duplex workflow that combines the two platforms in parallel:

1. CDC Flu SC2 Multiplex – Retained as the primary panel for routine community-wide surveillance of influenza A/B and SARS-CoV-2, ensuring continuity of the current public-health reporting system.
2. JRC-HA and JRC-MP Duplex – Deployed alongside the CDC panel to specifically identify and confirm the occurrence of HPAI A(H5N1).3.4.4b virus in a population, providing an early-warning capability that is effective also in the presence of seasonal-influenza backgrounds.

Given the validated performance of this combined approach and the current heightened risk of HPAI circulation, we suggest the adoption of the dual-duplex protocol in high-risk regions to enhance wastewater-based epidemiology and pandemic preparedness.

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Data availability

All data presented in the manuscript or supplementary material are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflict of interest

The scientific output expressed does not imply a policy position of the European Commission. Neither the European Commission nor any person acting on behalf of the Commission is responsible for the use that might be made of the information contained in this publication. The authors declare no competing interests.

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Ethical statement

Not applicable

Use of artificial intelligence tools

None declared

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